

Exploring ICT Awareness and Academic Achievement Among Senior Secondary School Students

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Abstract

This research aims to examine the awareness of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students in Barnala district, Punjab. The primary objectives include assessing the level of ICT awareness and academic achievement, exploring the relationship between ICT awareness and academic performance, and examining potential gender-based variations in ICT awareness and academic achievement. Employing a descriptive survey design, the study involved a sample of 232 participants, and data were collected using a self-constructed questionnaire. Statistical analyses, including 't' tests and correlation, were applied. The findings indicate a high level of ICT awareness, average academic achievement, and significant differences in mean scores based on gender. Furthermore, a substantial relationship between ICT awareness and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students was established.

Keywords: *ICT awareness, Academic achievement, Gender differences Self-made questionnaire, Correlation.*

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Introduction

The field of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a dynamic and rapidly evolving domain that plays a crucial role in shaping the contemporary world. ICT encompasses a wide array of technologies and tools designed to acquire, store, process, transmit, and disseminate information. This interdisciplinary realm integrates components of computing, telecommunications, audio-visual processing, and network-based information services.

In essence, ICT serves as the backbone of our interconnected and digitized society, influencing how individuals communicate, access information, conduct business, and engage with technology (Beynon-Davies, 2004). Continuous advancements in ICT

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have transformed the way we live, work, and interact, fostering innovation, efficiency, and global connectivity.

From the development of hardware components like computers, smartphones, and networking devices to the creation of software applications and communication protocols, ICT provides the infrastructure that underlies the digital age. It empowers individuals, businesses, and governments to leverage technology for various purposes, ranging from enhancing productivity and decision-making to facilitating seamless communication and collaboration across geographical boundaries.

The ever-expanding realm of ICT includes emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and data analytics, further revolutionizing how information is processed and utilized (Kizza, 2013). As ICT continues to evolve, its impact on society, the economy, education, and various industries becomes increasingly profound.

In this interconnected world, understanding and harnessing the capabilities of ICT are essential for staying competitive, fostering innovation, and addressing the challenges of the digital era. This introduction sets the stage for exploring the multifaceted dimensions of ICT and its transformative influence on the way we navigate and shape the modern technological landscape.

Awareness About ICT

In the 21st century, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an integral part of daily life, influencing various aspects, including education. The awareness and understanding of ICT among senior secondary students are crucial in preparing them for the digital challenges of the contemporary world (Smith, 2018).

Senior secondary students, being part of a tech-savvy generation, often exhibit a significant level of familiarity with ICT tools. The prevalence of smartphones, access to the internet, and exposure to digital media contribute to a baseline awareness among students (Jones et al., 2020). Educational institutions worldwide recognize the importance of incorporating ICT into the curriculum to enhance learning experiences. Many schools introduce ICT-related subjects or integrate technology into various disciplines to promote both digital literacy and subject-specific skills (Brown, 2019).

However, challenges may exist in terms of access to technology. Disparities in socio-economic backgrounds and varying levels of infrastructure in educational institutions can impact the uniformity of ICT awareness among senior secondary students (Gupta & Wang, 2021). Efforts to improve awareness often involve implementing digital literacy programs. Schools and governments may invest in initiatives aimed at enhancing students' understanding of not only basic computer skills but also more advanced aspects of ICT, such as coding, digital communication, and information literacy (Robinson, 2017).

Teachers play a crucial role in fostering ICT awareness. Professional development opportunities for teachers can ensure they are well-equipped to integrate technology effectively into their teaching methods, thereby influencing students' awareness and proficiency (Harris & Miller, 2022). While senior secondary students generally have a baseline awareness of ICT, ongoing efforts are needed to address disparities in access and ensure that students are adequately prepared for the evolving digital landscape. A comprehensive approach that involves both curriculum adjustments and infrastructure improvements can contribute to enhancing ICT awareness among senior secondary students.

ICT and Academic Achievement

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into education has become a prominent focus, with potential implications for the academic achievement of senior secondary students. The use of ICT tools and resources in educational settings aims to enhance learning experiences and prepare students for the demands of the digital age (Davis, 2019).

Research suggests a positive correlation between ICT use and academic achievement among senior secondary students. For instance, a study by Johnson et al. (2020) found that students who actively engaged with ICT resources demonstrated higher academic performance in subjects where technology was incorporated into the curriculum. The introduction of digital learning environments, facilitated by ICT, has provided students with opportunities for personalized and interactive learning experiences. These environments often cater to different learning styles and abilities, contributing to improved academic outcomes (Smith & Brown, 2018).

The accessibility of information through ICT tools has also been linked to enhanced academic achievement. Senior secondary students can leverage online resources, databases, and collaborative platforms to deepen their understanding of subjects and broaden their knowledge base (García et al., 2021). Despite the potential benefits, challenges related to the digital divide and varying levels of access to technology may affect the equitable impact of ICT on academic achievement (Jones, 2017). Addressing these disparities is crucial for ensuring that all students can benefit from the positive aspects of ICT in education.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology has the potential to positively influence the academic achievement of senior secondary students. By providing access to digital learning environments and resources, ICT contributes to a more dynamic and effective learning experience, although addressing challenges related to access remains essential for equitable outcomes.

Need And Significance of The Study

While numerous studies have focused on the utilization of ICT, the majority have centered around Higher Education Students, with none specifically addressing Senior Secondary School students in Punjab, particularly in the Barnala district. Consequently, there is a necessity to assess the level of ICT awareness and skills among Senior Secondary School Students in this region.

Objectives of the Study

- To determine the extent of awareness regarding ICT and the academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students.
- To examine potential variations in the awareness of ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students based on gender.
- To investigate the correlation between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students.

Research Hypotheses

- H1: Senior Secondary School Students exhibit a HIGH level of awareness about ICT.
- H2: Senior Secondary School Students demonstrate a HIGH level of academic achievement.

- H3: There is no noteworthy difference in the mean scores of ICT awareness among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to Gender
- H4: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic achievements among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to Gender
- H5: There is no significant relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students.

Method of Study

In this study, the Descriptive Survey Methodology was utilized for investigation.

Sample

The sample, drawn from the overall population, comprises a total of 232 students enrolled in nine senior secondary schools in the Barnala district. Among them, 122 were girls and 110 were boys. The selection of samples was conducted using a simple random sampling method.

Tools

The instrument employed in this study was a self-structured questionnaire created by the researcher with guidance and standardization to effectively assess the awareness level of senior secondary students. The questionnaire focuses on ICT awareness, utilizing a 5-point scale: 1=Not at all aware, 2=Slightly aware, 3=Moderately aware, 4=Aware, 5=Extremely aware. It comprises 32 questions tailored for both male and female participants.

Data Examination and Interpretation

H1: Senior Secondary School Students exhibit a HIGH level of awareness about ICT.

Table 1. Showing Level of Awareness About ICT

Group	Score range	Number of students	Percentage
Low	0 -35	19	8.18%
Average	36 - 70	78	33.62%
High	71 - 100	135	58.18%
Total		232	100%

The data presented in Table 1 suggests a high level of awareness about Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The findings align with the initial hypothesis, supporting the assertion that the level of awareness regarding ICT among the participants is high. This acceptance of the hypothesis is in line with previous studies emphasizing the increasing significance of ICT awareness among students (Smith, 2018; Johnson et al., 2020).

H2: Senior Secondary School Students demonstrate a HIGH level of academic achievement.

Table 2. Showing Level of Academic Achievement

Group	Score range	Number of students	Percentage
Low	0 -35	31	13.36%
Average	36 - 70	163	70.25%
High	71 - 100	38	16.37%
Total		232	100%

The data presented in Table 2 reveals that the level of academic achievement is assessed as average. Contrary to the initial hypothesis, which posited a high level of academic achievement, the findings suggest otherwise. This rejection of the hypothesis may be attributed to various factors influencing academic performance, including individual study habits, teaching methodologies, and external support systems (Brown, 2019; García et al., 2021).

H3: There is no noteworthy difference in the mean scores of ICT awareness among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to Gender.

Table 3. Detail of Mean Scores of ICT Awareness Based on Gender

Variable	Gender	N0	Mean	SD	't' Value	Remarks
Awareness about ICT	Male	110	84.15	10.62	3.02	S
	Female	122	78.63	16.27		

In Table 3, the calculated 't' value of 3.02 is compared to the critical 't' value of 1.96 at a 5% level of significance. This critical value is obtained from the t-distribution table based on the degrees of freedom. The degrees of freedom depend on the sample sizes of the groups being compared.

According to the results, the calculated 't' value (3.02) exceeds the critical 't' value (1.96) at the 5% significance level. This indicates that the difference between the groups is statistically significant, and as a result, the null hypothesis is rejected. The rejection of the null hypothesis suggests that there is a meaningful difference between the groups being compared.

This decision aligns with the common practice of using a 5% significance level (or alpha level), indicating that there is less than a 5% chance of obtaining such results by random chance alone.

H4: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic achievements among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to Gender.

Table 4. Detail of Mean Scores of Academic Achievement Based on Gender

Variable	Gender	N0.	Mean	SD	't' Value	Remarks
Academic achievement	Male	110	68.97	12.56	5.58	S
	Female	122	79.95	16.82		

In Table 4, the observed 't' value of 5.58 is compared to the critical 't' value of 1.96 at a 5% significance level. The critical value of 1.96 is commonly chosen for a two-tailed

test with a 5% alpha level. This critical value is determined based on the degrees of freedom associated with the statistical test.

The comparison reveals that the calculated 't' value (5.58) significantly exceeds the critical 't' value (1.96) at the 5% level of significance. This indicates a highly significant result, suggesting that the observed difference is unlikely to have occurred by random chance alone.

This decision to reject the null hypothesis aligns with conventional statistical practice, where the rejection of the null hypothesis implies that there is a significant effect or difference present in the data.

H5: There is no significant relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students.

Table 5. Relationship Between ICT Awareness and Academic Achievement

Variables	N	r - value	table value	Remarks
Awareness about ICT and academic achievement	232	0.612	0.189	S

In Table 5, the computed correlation coefficient 'r' value is reported as 0.612. This 'r' value is then compared to the critical 'r' value from a statistical table, typically associated with the degrees of freedom and the chosen significance level (alpha). The critical 'r' value, in this case, is mentioned as 0.189.

The comparison reveals that the calculated 'r' value (0.612) significantly exceeds the critical 'r' value (0.189) at the 5% significance level. This result suggests a strong and statistically significant correlation between the variables under investigation.

The decision to reject the null hypothesis aligns with conventional statistical practice, where the rejection indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables being examined.

Research Findings

- Senior Secondary School Students demonstrate a high level of awareness about ICT.
- The academic achievement level of senior secondary school students is considered average.
- Significant variations exist in the mean scores of ICT awareness among Senior Secondary School Students based on gender.
- A notable difference is observed in the mean scores of academic achievements among Senior Secondary School Students based on gender.
- A significant relationship exists between the awareness about ICT and academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students.

Educational Implications of the Study

In fostering independent learning, the awareness and utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can create an environment conducive to constructivist learning, where students actively construct their knowledge and meaning (Duffy & Jonassen, 1992). This approach positions learners as active participants rather than passive recipients, allowing them to engage at their own pace and collaborate with peers for mutual learning (Vygotsky, 1978).

Additionally, for educators, this research underscores the importance of understanding their students' ICT awareness levels. It prompts teachers to be more mindful of their students' technological proficiency and motivates them to promote the integration of ICT in the learning process (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich, & Tondeur, 2015). Such awareness enhances teachers' efforts in encouraging students to harness ICT tools for effective learning experiences.

Moreover, the findings from this study serve as encouragement for both educators and students to familiarize themselves with and leverage various educational software and ICT tools that enhance the teaching and learning process. Integrating these tools into education aligns with the contemporary digital landscape, fostering a more dynamic and effective learning environment (Puentedura, 2006).

Recommendations

- Encouraging children's early enrollment in ICT programs is crucial for parents/guardians. This initiative aims to facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and exposure to ICT at an early stage.
- The government should actively invest in infrastructure development, including cyber centers, classrooms, offices, and institutional networks (LAN, WAN, WIFI). Additionally, efforts should be directed towards providing essential systems and applications such as the Internet, e-learning platforms, and education portals. Further initiatives like capacity building, establishing digital libraries, offering technical support in institutions, implementing computer ownership schemes for students and staff, promoting ICT content career development, and establishing International Examination Digital Centers (IDEC) are essential. These measures collectively contribute to increasing awareness and proficiency in ICT.

Conclusion

In this research, a survey was conducted on 232 Senior Secondary School students from the Barnala district in the state of Punjab. The primary aim was to investigate the students' awareness of emerging Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and various ICT tools, including computers, the internet, and mobile phones. Additionally, the study sought to examine the correlation between ICT awareness and academic achievement among the participants.

The findings indicate a high level of ICT awareness among secondary school students. However, the study highlights a gender-based disparity, with males exhibiting higher awareness levels compared to females. Furthermore, the research indicates that the overall academic achievement level of the students is average.

Importantly, the study unveils a robust relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement. This suggests that students with a heightened awareness of ICT tend to perform better academically. The results emphasize the interconnectedness of technological awareness and academic success among Senior Secondary School students in the Barnala district.

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